

BP 15/07/2020 V.01

BUKU PANDUAN WEB FORUM PPTIK

PPTIK ITB

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WEBSITE FORUM PPTIK

Buka website forum PPTIK – ITB di link berikut : <http://forum.pptik.id/>

Di dalam website akan menampilkan beberapa produk PPTIK-ITB dan forum untuk membicarakan masalah teknis.

Website ①

Klik link diatas lalu akan masuk ke dalam web seperti gambar di samping. Web tersebut akan menampilkan beberapa pengenalan produk PPTIK - ITB, informasi mengenai acara yang dilakukan PPTIK - ITB dan beberapa informasi lainnya

Registrasi ②

Yang pertama dilakukan adalah mendaftarkan atau meregistrasi akun dengan cara klik "REGISTER"

Register →

PPTIK FORUM - Registration Agreement

Whilst we attempt to edit or remove any messages containing inappropriate, sexually orientated, abusive, hateful, slanderous, or threatening material that could be considered invasive of a person's privacy, or which otherwise violate any kind of law, it is impossible for us to review every message posted on this discussion system. For this reason you acknowledge that all messages posted on this discussion system express the views and opinions of the original message author and not necessarily the views of this bulletin board. Therefore we take no responsibility and cannot be held liable for any messages posted. We do not vouch for or warrant the accuracy and completeness of every message.

By registering on this discussion system you agree that you will not post any material which is knowingly false, inaccurate, abusive, hateful, harassing, sexually orientated, threatening or invasive of a person's privacy, or any other material which may violate any applicable laws.

Failure to comply with these rules may result in the termination of your account, account suspension, or permanent ban of access to these forums. Your IP Address is recorded with each post you make on this discussion system and is retrievable by the forum staff if need-be. You agree that we have the ability and right to remove, edit, or lock any account or message at any time should it be seen fit. You also agree that any information you enter on this discussion system is stored in a database, and that "cookies" are stored on your computer to save your login information.

Any information you provide on these forums will not be disclosed to any third party without your complete consent, although the staff cannot be held liable for any hacking attempt in which your data is compromised.

By continuing with the sign up process you agree to the above rules and any others that the Administrator specifies.

I Agree

Registrasi ③

Setelah men-klik register maka akan muncul seperti gambar di atas yang berisi tentang "Registration Agreement". Jika sudah membaca lalu klik "I Agree". Lalu akan muncul seperti gambar di bawah untuk mendaftarkan akun anda

Registration

Account Details

Username:

Password: Confirm Password:

Email: Confirm Email:

Referrer:

If you were referred to these forums by another member you can enter their name below. If not, simply leave this field blank.

Search for a user

Image Verification

Please enter the text contained within the image into the text box below it. This process is used to prevent automated spam bots.

 (case insensitive)

Refresh

Security Question

Please answer the question provided. This process is used to prevent automated processes.

What does 2 + 2 equal?

Account Preferences:

- Receive emails from the Administrators.
- Hide your email from other members.
- Receive private messages from other users.
- Alert me with a notice when I receive a Private Message.
- Notify me by email when I receive a new Private Message.
- Hide me from the Who's Online list.

Default Thread Subscription Mode:

Time Zone (DST correction excluded):

If you live in a time zone which differs to what this board is set at, you can select it from the list below.

GMT (09:00 AM)

Daylight Saving Time correction:

Submit Registration!

Registration

Account Details

Username:

Password: Confirm Password:

Email: Confirm Email:

Referrer:

If you were referred to these forums by another member you can enter their name below. If not, simply leave this field blank.

Image Verification

Please enter the text contained within the image into the text box below it. This process is used to prevent automated spam bots.

(case insensitive)

Security Question

Please answer the question provided. This process is used to prevent automated processes.

What does 2 + 2 equal?

Registrasi ④

Masukkan data diri di “Account Details” dengan menuliskan Username, Password dan email

Lalu isi “Image Verification” dengan mengikuti gambar yang berada di sebelah kanan.

Isi “Security Question” dengan memasukkan isi dari pertanyaan yang tertera

Registrasi ⑤

Lalu pilih “Time Zone” sesuai dengan lokasi anda berada dan pilih Automatically Detect DST Settings di “Daylight Saving Time Correction”

Account Preferences:

- Receive emails from the Administrators.
- Hide your email from other members.
- Receive private messages from other users.
- Alert me with a notice when I receive a Private Message.
- Notify me by email when I receive a new Private Message.
- Hide me from the Who's Online list.

Default Thread Subscription Mode:

Time Zone (DST correction excluded):

If you live in a time zone which differs to what this board is set at, you can select it from the list below.

Daylight Saving Time correction:

Registration

Account Details

Username: sintiar28

Password: ***** Confirm Password: *****

Email: sintiarahmawati31@gmail.com Confirm Email: sintiarahmawati31@gmail.com

Referrer:

If you were referred to these forums by another member you can enter their name below. If not, simply leave this field blank.

Search for a user

Image Verification

Please enter the text contained within the image into the text box below it. This process is used to prevent automated spam bots.

cYjrd
(case insensitive)

cyjrd Refresh

Security Question

Please answer the question provided. This process is used to prevent automated processes.

What does 2 + 2 equal?
4

Account Preferences:

- Receive emails from the Administrators.
- Hide your email from other members.
- Receive private messages from other users.
- Alert me with a notice when I receive a Private Message.
- Notify me by email when I receive a new Private Message.
- Hide me from the Who's Online list.

Default Thread Subscription Mode:
Do not subscribe

Time Zone (DST correction excluded):

If you live in a time zone which differs to what this board is set at, you can select it from the list below.

GMT +7:00 (04:00 PM)

Daylight Saving Time correction:
Automatically detect DST settings

Submit Registration!

Activate Windows

Submit Registration!

Registrasi ⑥

Setelah semua sudah terisi dengan lengkap periksa kembali. Dan jika sudah benar lalu klik "Submit Registration !" untuk membuat akun anda.

Jika sudah maka akan muncul seperti gambar di bawah lalu klik "Login" untuk masuk ke dalam akun anda.

PPTIK - ITB
Pusat Penelitian Teknologi Informasi dan Komunikasi
Institut Teknologi Bandung

Portal Search Member List Calendar Help

Hello There, Guest! **Login** Register

PPTIK FORUM
Board Message

PPTIK FORUM

Thank you for registering on PPTIK FORUM, sintiar28.

To complete your registration, please check your email for account activation instructions. Until you activate your account you may not be able to post on these forums

Tweet Like 3 Share

LOGIN ⑦

Masukkan Username dan Password yang sudah dibuat seperti gambar di samping lalu klik “LOGIN”

PPTIK FORUM

Forum ⑧

Jika sudah masuk ke dalam akun dan muncul seperti gambar di atas tidak perlu khawatir kita hanya perlu klik “PPTIK FORUM” untuk membuka halamam forum

Forum PKL Online 9

Setelah masuk kedalam forum seperti gambar di samping. Untuk mengetahui informasi tentang PKL Online klik “PKL Online”

Welcome back, sintiar28. You last visited: Today, 02:12 PM Log Out →

User CP View New Posts View Today's Posts

PPTIK FORUM

Learning Material
Learning Material

Forum	Threads	Posts	Last Post
Internet of Things Sub Forums: Basic Internet of Things, Sistem Mikroprocessor untuk IOT, and 6 more.	2	2	MODUL WORKSHOP LORA ANTAR... 06-04-2020, 11:52 AM by Agus Sukoco
3D Computer Graphics & Virtual Reality	6	21	Holokit Development 07-06-2020, 01:43 PM by vpratama
Human-Content Interaction	0	0	Never
Artificial General Intelligence	1	2	AirSim - Open source simu... Yesterday, 02:45 PM by vpratama

Workshop, Discussion & Courses
Forum untuk mendiskusikan apa-apa yang terjadi di Workshop, Diskusi Umum dan beberapa Kuliah yang diselenggarakan oleh PPTIK

Forum	Threads	Posts	Last Post
Workshop IOT Tempat berdiskusi tentang pelaksanaan Workshop IOT yang diselenggarakan oleh PPTIK Sub Forums: Sigfox IOT Devices & System, Lora-based IOT Device, and 1 more.	1	1	Perkembangan SigFox di Th... 07-13-2020, 06:49 PM by L. Kadir
PKL Online Sub Forums: Magang Guru, PKL Online Siswa, and 1 more.	3	30	Sosialisasi PKL Online 55 minutes ago by sintiar27
Kerja Praktek di PPTIK	8	8	KP di PPTIK: Rule of The ... 06-14-2020, 08:55 AM by ssetiadi

PKL Online
Sub Forums: Magang Guru, PKL Online Siswa, and 1 more.

Forum PKL Online 10

Di dalam PKL Online terdapat beberapa menu yaitu ada “Magang Guru”, “PKL Online Siswa” dan ada “Sosialisasi” dan adapun komunikasi antara pihak PPTIK dengan beberapa Guru yang sebelumnya sudah terdaftar.

Welcome back, sintiar28. You last visited: Today, 02:12 PM Log Out →

User CP View New Posts View Today's Posts

PPTIK FORUM > Workshop, Discussion & Courses
PKL Online

Users browsing this forum: sintiar28

Forums in 'PKL Online'

Forum	Threads	Posts	Last Post
Magang Guru Sub Forums: Prosedur, Ketentuan, and 1 more.	0	0	Never
PKL Online Siswa Sub Forums: Prosedur, Ketentuan, and 1 more.	0	0	Never
Sosialisasi	1	1	Sosialisasi PKL Online 58 minutes ago by sintiar27

PKL Online Mark this forum read | Subscribe to this forum

Thread / Author	Replies	Views	Rating	Last Post [asc]
Teknis PKL Online siti_fatmawati	3	78	☆☆☆☆☆	07-14-2020, 10:39 AM Last Post: siti_fatmawati
Pengumuman Terkini (Pages: 1 2 3) rifawigjaya	24	699	☆☆☆☆☆	07-13-2020, 09:48 PM Last Post: Nur Janah

Sort by: Last Post Order: Descending From: The Beginning Go

Sosialisasi 11

Setelah masuk kedalam forum seperti gambar di samping. Untuk mengetahui informasi tentang PKL Online klik "PKL Online"

Forums in 'PKL Online'

Forum	Threads	Posts	Last Post
Magang Guru Sub Forums: Prosedur , Ketentuan , and 1 more.	0	0	Never
PKL Online Siswa Sub Forums: Prosedur , Ketentuan , and 1 more.	0	0	Never
Sosialisasi	1	1	Sosialisasi PKL Online 1 hour ago by sintiar27

PKL Online [Mark this forum read](#) | [Subscribe to this forum](#)

Thread / Author	Replies	Views	Rating	Last Post [asc]
Teknis PKL Online siti_fatmawati	3	78	☆☆☆☆☆	07-14-2020, 10:39 AM Last Post: siti_fatmawati
Pengumuman Terkini (Pages: 1 2 3) rifkiwijaya	24	699	☆☆☆☆☆	07-13-2020, 09:48 PM Last Post: Nur Janah

Sort by: Last Post | Order: Descending | From: The Beginning | Go

PPTIK FORUM > Workshop, Discussion & Courses > PKL Online
↳ **Sosialisasi**

Users browsing this forum: sintiar28

Sosialisasi [Mark this forum read](#) | [Subscribe to this forum](#)

Thread / Author	Replies	Views	Rating	Last Post [asc]
Sosialisasi PKL Online sintiar27	0	4	☆☆☆☆☆	1 hour ago Last Post: sintiar27

Sort by: Last Post | Order: Descending | From: The Beginning | Go

Informasi 12

Ini adalah tampilan dari Sosialisasi PKL Online

Sosialisasi PKL Online Thread Modes

[sintiar27](#) Administrator
☆☆☆☆☆

1 hour ago (This post was last modified: 4 minutes ago by sintiar27.) #1

Have a good day everyone..... 😊

PPTIK hadir dalam untuk memberikan solusi terkait dengan PKL yang tetap bisa dilaksanakan tana harus bertatap muka. Biasanya proses PKL yang dilakukan oleh siswa adalah dengan datang ke industri ataupun tempat yang sudah ditentukan sekolah namun kali ini berbeda. Dengan kondisi Indonesia yang sekarang ini masih tidak diperbolehkan untuk bertemu dengan banyak orang atau berkumpul di suatu ruangan maka segala sesuatunya harus online supaya menghindari diri dari kerumunan.

Dalam kondisi sekarang siswa akan sulit untuk menemukan industri pun tidak akan membuka kesempatan untuk melaksanakan kegiatan PKL karena industri harus mematuhi dan menjalankan aturan yang sudah dibuat oleh pemerintah. Sehingga ada beberapa siswa yang tidak bisa menjalankan PKL, yang mana PKL sendiri juga merupakan point terpenting dari penilaian di SMK. Karena dari PKL siswa diperkenalkan dengan industri dan juga dapat menambah skil dalam mengerjakan tugas yang sudah diberikan.

Untuk penjelasan lebih lanjut mengenai PKL Online bisa dilihat di link berikut <https://ot.pptik.id/2020/07/16/mekanisme-pkl-online/>

Sosialisasi tentang PKL Online ini sebelumnya sudah dilakukan oleh kami dengan melakukan video conferences dengan guru guru SMK dari diberbagai penjuru Indonesia.

